

The Otomi

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Mesoamerican Religions, Language, Otomanguean, Western Otomanguean, Otopame-Chinantecan, Otopamean, Otomian, Otomi

The Otomi are among the oldest Indigenous civilizations in central Mexico, often regarded as the earliest inhabitants of the high plains. Their rich history spans thousands of years, with a deeply rooted social structure that has evolved over time. Their religious practices were shaped by a complex cosmology, where gods were associated with natural elements such as the sun, rain, and earth, with complex rituals and religious ceremonies held to honor these deities. Their connection to the natural world is reflected in a structured clan-based system, where different groups held spiritual significance tied to specific elements or celestial bodies. Their religious worldview was not only a matter of spirituality but also a guiding force in their daily lives, and their religious ceremonies were often central to community gatherings and political decision-making. They used visual symbols, including murals and codices, to represent their gods and cosmic beliefs, which also played a role in social cohesion. Despite centuries of external pressures, including Spanish colonization, many aspects of their religion are still practiced to this day.

Date Range: 5000 BCE - 1519 CE

Region: High Central plains of Mexico

Region tags: North America, Mesoamerica and the Caribbean, Mexico

The Otomi language and culture is concentrated in the High Central Plains of Mexico

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Fuente 1: Galinier, J. *La Mitad Del Mundo: Cuerpo y Cosmos En Los Rituales Otomíes*. Mexico: UNAM, 1990.
- Fuente 2: Correa, P.M. "Otomí Rituals and Celebrations: Crosses, Ancestors, and Resurrection." *The Journal of American Folklore* 113, no. 450 (2000): 436-50.
- Fuente 3: López Austin, A., and L. López Luján. *El Pasado Indígena*. Mexico: Fondo de Cultura Económica, 2001.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- URL de la Fuente 1: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3538330>
- Descripción de la Fuente 1: Cornejo Cabrera, E. "Los Otomíes: Historia Del Grupo y de La Cultura y Su Situación Actual." *Revista Mexicana de Sociología* 87, no. 1 (1961): 55-90
- URL de la Fuente 2: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319515504_The_three_souls_of_the_Otomi
- Descripción de la Fuente 2: Wright Carr, D. "The Three Souls of the Otomi." *Acta Classica*, no. 53 (2017): 179-95
- URL de la Fuente 3: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/23611395_Lengua_cultura_e_historia_de_los_otomies
- Descripción de la Fuente 3: Wright Carr, D.C. "Lengua, Cultura e Historia de Los Otomíes." *Arqueología Mexicana*, no. 73 (2005): 26-29

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- URL de la Fuente 1: <https://books.google.es/books?hl=es&lr=&id=9VBbzgLLk2kC&oi=fnd&pg=PA9&dq=otomi+religion+descripcion&ots=6hg6gPoYzP&sig=26oPrVgtdS9wXc2BGQ4raltuHi4#v=onepage&q=>
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- Descripción de la Fuente 2: Carrasco Pizana, P. *Los Otomíes. Cultura e Historia de Los Pueblos Mesoamericanos de Habla Otomiana*. Toluca: Gobierno del Estado de Mexico, 1986
- URL de la Fuente 3: <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.inpi.gob.mx/2021/estudios/cdi-estudio-general-del-pueblo-otomi.pdf>
- Descripción de la Fuente 3: Matías Lara, J.C., G. Ramírez Ramos, V. Peñaloza Moreno, and D. Perez Gonzalez. *Pueblos Indígenas de México En El Siglo XXI. Otomí. Estudio General al Pueblo Otomí*. Edited by L. Baez Cubero and C. Garrett Rios. Mexico: INPI, 2016.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

— Sí

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

— Sí

Notes: Before the European invasion, the Matlatzincó Valley, known as the Hñá Hñu region in what is now the State of Mexico, displayed a complex cultural and linguistic landscape due to constant migrations of various Indigenous populations. This region, traditionally inhabited by Otomian groups, was regarded by the Tenochcas as an expansive granary irrigated by the Chignahuatenco River, now known as the Lerma River. Beginning in 1470, the Tenochcas initiated the military conquest of the area, employing a staggered strategy of subjugation against rebellious lordships. Among the consequences of this process were the exodus of the Náhñu people to territories controlled by other ethnic groups, such as the Tarascans and Chichimecas, and the Nahua repopulation of the area. (Galinier, 1990; Lopez Austin & Lopez Lujan, 2001; Wright Carr, Lara Valdés & Contreras Soto, 2010)

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

— No

Notes: The Otomi religion was deeply integrated into the social and cultural structure of the community. Religious affiliation was not assigned through a formal process but was naturally transmitted through family and community ties. (Carrasco, 1990)

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

— El campo lo desconoce

Notes: There is no evidence that the Otomi actively engaged in proselytism to recruit new members. Their religion was ethnic and communal, centered on traditions and practices shared within their group. The bádi - Otomi Shamans - would usually indoctrinate the children routinely inside the temples. (Dyckerhoff, 1984)

Does the religion have official political support

— Sí

Notes: In pre-Hispanic Mesoamerican societies, religion and politics were in constant contact. Otomi political leaders often played religious roles, and religious practices helped legitimize political authority. Consequently, the Otomi religion had official support from community political leaders. (Lopez Austin & Lopez Lujan, 2001; Lastra, 2006)

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

— El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Since religion was intrinsically tied to community and cultural identity, abandoning traditional religious practices was likely viewed negatively, though there is no evidence of a structured notion of apostasy akin to that of later organized religions, like Christianity. (Galinier, 1990)

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

— El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Exact population figures for the pre-Hispanic Otomi remain unknown, but archaeological research suggests their numbers may have reached several hundred thousand, occupying vast regions of what are now the states of Mexico, Hidalgo, Puebla, Querétaro, and parts of Guanajuato. (Villegas et al., 1994)

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

— El campo lo desconoce

Notes: The pre-Hispanic Otomi population was spread across multiple lordships, including Xilotepec and Tollan, where religious practices were closely woven into the fabric of community life. It is reasonable to assume that the majority of the population engaged in traditional Otomi religion, making it likely that the number of adherents aligned with the overall population, estimated to be in the hundreds of thousands. (Lopez Austin & Lopez Lujan, 2001)

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

— No

Notes: The pre-Hispanic Otomi did not have a writing system for sacred texts. Instead of written

scriptures, religious traditions were primarily transmitted orally through stories, rituals, and ceremonies conducted by priests or community leaders. (Wright Carr, Lara Valdés & Contreras Soto, 2010)

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Sí

Notes: The Otomi built notable structures, including pyramids and platforms, which had ritual and ceremonial functions. These structures were mainly found in key sites like Xilotepec, Cañada de la Virgen and Tollan, both of which held significance in the Otomi worldview and political-religious structure. Their architecture was aligned with the symbolism of the cosmic cycle and nature deities. (Kirchhoff, 2000; Zepeda García Moreno, 2005)

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Sí

↳ Tombs:

– Sí

Notes: While funeral practices in Otomi culture are less documented compared to other Mesoamerican cultures, there is evidence of funerary structures linked to their religious beliefs. Tombs found at sites such as Xilotepec and Tollan contained burials accompanied by offerings and were situated within platforms or pyramids. These tombs were often oriented towards specific cardinal points, highlighting the significance of the connection between death and the cosmos. (Wright Carr, Lara Valdés & Contreras Soto, 2010)

↳ Cemeteries:

– Sí

Notes: Cemeteries in Otomi territory were likely small and spread across different locations, rather than concentrated near large urban centers. They were often situated near temples or ritual areas, with tombs that included offerings and ceremonial items. They likely were sacred spaces dedicated to honoring the dead, fostering spiritual ties between the living and the deceased. (Lopez Austin & Lopez Lujan, 2001)

↳ Temples:

– Sí

Notes: Temples were the most significant forms of monumental architecture for the Otomi. Typically pyramidal or platform-shaped, these structures served as centers of worship and were dedicated to various deities. Their orientation was aligned with astronomical and cosmological principles, intended to highlight the connection between the spiritual and physical realms. (Kirchhoff, 2000)

↳ Altars:

– Sí

Notes: Altars were essential spaces in Otomi religious architecture. Typically located on platforms or at the tops of pyramids, these altars were used for sacrifices and offerings to the deities. They represented points of direct contact between humans and gods, and were spaces of significant ritual importance. (Wright Carr, Lara Valdés & Contreras Soto, 2010)

↳ Devotional markers:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Sí

Notes: Plazas and open spaces, which served as mass gathering sites, were common in Otomi urban centers. These areas were used for major ceremonies, rituals, and celebrations. Surrounded by monumental structures like temples and altars, the plazas acted as focal points where the community gathered for worship, trade, and to strengthen both political and religious ties. (Kirchhoff, 2000)

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– El campo lo desconoce

Is iconography present:

– Sí

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- En el hogar
- En algunos espacios públicos

Notes: Religious symbols, depictions of gods and deities, and mythological figures were present in reliefs, ceramics, sculptures, and mural paintings. In sites like Tollan, evidence of sculptures and reliefs has been found that depict mythological and cult scenes, as well as figures associated with the forces of nature and the cosmic cycle. (Lopez Austin & Lopez Lujan, 2001)

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Sí

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Sí

Notes: Eyes are recurring symbols in Otomi iconography, representing perception and connection with the divine. They appear in various artifacts and representations, highlighting the importance of vision in spiritual understanding. (Galinier, 2011)

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Sí

Notes: The representation of supernatural beings with animal characteristics is common. For example, in Otomi rock art, figures of herons and deer are fairly common and usually symbolize spiritual and ritual aspects of the culture. (Peña Salinas, 2019)

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Sí

Notes: Eyes are recurring symbols in Otomi iconography, representing perception and connection with the divine. They often appear in various artifacts and representations. (Galinier, 2011)

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Sí

Notes: The human figure is also represented in Otomi iconography, especially in ritual and ceremonial scenes. (Peña Salinas, NA)

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Sí

Notes: Supernatural beings (abstract symbol): Abstract symbols representing supernatural entities can be observed, such as geometric patterns that may refer to cosmic or spiritual forces. These symbols reflect the complexity and depth of Otomi spirituality. (Galinier, 2011)

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Sí

Notes: Human representations in Otomi iconography include figures of warriors, priests, and other individuals in ritual scenes. (Hernández Dávila, 2019)

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Sí

Notes: Otomi iconography also includes representations of temples, altars, and other architectural elements. (Peña Salinas, 2019; Hernández Dávila, 2019)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Sí

Notes: The Otomi religion speaks of a distinction between the physical body and a spiritual essence, often tied to animistic beliefs and the connection with natural forces and deities. (Wright Carr, Lara Valdés & Contreras Soto, 2010) Additionally, The vital force of beings of any type, called nzahki, allows controlling and manipulating what happens in the world. Only the badi (shamans) can interact with it, cutting out figures in amate paper with which they invoke the powers. (Barona Tovar, 2002)

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Sí

Notes: The Otomi believe in multiple soul essences, which have distinct properties compared to the physical body. These essences can exist independently of the body and play specific roles in life and death. (Wright-Carr, 2016)

Belief in afterlife:

– Sí

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Sí

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Sí

Notes: In Otomi belief, the afterlife is often associated with a spiritual realm below the earth. This is common in many Mesoamerican cultures, where the dead are thought to travel to a lower realm after death. This space is not necessarily evil or dark, but a realm where spirits undergo transformation, possibly in connection to deities or ancestors. (Galinier, 1990; Lopez Austin, 1988)

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: There is no explicit evidence of a belief in reincarnation in the sense of returning to the physical world in a new body. (Sandstrom & Hugo, 2005)

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Sí

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Sí (especifique): Placement of offerings

Notes: The Otomi performed specific burial rituals to aid the deceased's journey to the afterlife, including placing offerings such as food and pottery in the tomb. (Galinier, 1990; Lopez Austin, 1988)

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence that suggests the presence of co-sacrifices in Otomi burial practices, unlike in other Mesoamerican cultures.

Are grave goods present:

– Sí

↳ Personal effects:

– Sí

Notes: It is common to find the deceased's personal items, such as polished stone tools and awls, reflecting their daily life and role within the community. (Olivares Osorio, 2023)

↳ Valuable items:

– Sí

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– No

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Sí

Notes: Green stones and other valuable objects have been found in graves, indicating the importance of these items in beliefs related to the afterlife. (Olivares Osorio, 2023)

- ↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:
 - No
 - ↳ Other grave goods:
 - Sí

Notes: Burial sites included offerings such as ceramics, food, and other symbolic items. They were believed to assist the soul in its journey. (Galinier, 1990)
- Are formal burials present:
- Sí

Notes: Formal burial sites have been found in archaeological sites such as the Cañada de la Virgen (Zepeda García Moreno, 2005)
 - ↳ As cenotaphs:
 - No

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest that the Otomi used cenotaphs in their burial practices.
 - ↳ In cemetery:
 - Sí

Notes: The Otomi had designated burial grounds or cemeteries where formal burials took place. (Correa, 2000; Fitzsimmons & Shimada, 2011; Overholtzer, 2015; De Lucia, 2014) Burial sites have been found in Huamango, among other places.
 - ↳ Family tomb-crypt:
 - El campo lo desconoce

Notes: There is insufficient information to confirm whether the Otomi used family tombs or crypts.
 - ↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):
 - Sí

Notes: The Otomi practiced domestic burials, interring individuals beneath their homes or in areas associated with daily life. (Correa, 2000; Fitzsimmons & Shimada, 2011)
 - ↳ Other formal burial type:
 - Sí (especifique): Temples of Sacred Spaces

Notes: Formal burials often took place in ceremonial contexts, such as within temples or sacred spaces. In the Cañada de la Virgen site in Cuanajuato, burials were interred in areas associated with ritual and cosmic significance, such as the "House of the Thirteen Skies," which served as a ceremonial center. (Zepeda García Moreno, 2005)

Supernatural Beings

- Are supernatural beings present:
- Sí

Notes: The Otomi believe in a pantheon of deities, with the Old Mother and Old Father being central figures. The Old Mother is associated with the Earth and the Moon, embodying fertility, childbirth, and weaving, while the Old Father is linked to the Sun and Fire, representing strength, masculinity, and warmth. (Carrasco Pizana, 1986)
 - ↳ A supreme high god is present:
 - Sí

Notes: "Madre Vieja" and "Padre Viejo" represent the supreme divine figures in Otomi belief, manifesting as the primordial mother and father of humanity (Dow, 1974; García, 1918).
 - ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
 - Sí

Notes: "Madre Vieja" and "Padre Viejo" are depicted in human-like forms (Dow, 1974; García, 1918).
 - ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - Sí

Notes: The supreme gods are associated with celestial elements, such as the moon, sky and stars (Dow, 1974; García, 1918).

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - Sí
 - Notes: In some interpretations, the supreme god has a familial connection with elites, particularly as the head of a divine family. (Dow, 1974; García, 1918).
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - Sí (específico): The bādi
 - Notes: The bādi - Otomi Shaman - would often act as the middleman between the Otomi and their Gods. (Barona Tovar, 2002)
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Sí
 - Notes: The supreme gods are generally seen as benevolent, though their actions can be influenced by a larger cosmic balance. (Dow, 1974; García, 1918).
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Sí
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - El campo lo desconoce
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - El campo lo desconoce
 - Notes: The myths mention that the gods of the primordial couple influence human well-being, but their knowledge might be limited to these aspects within the communities. (Dow, 1974; García, 1918).
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Sí
 - Notes: The supreme gods' knowledge is unrestricted in its scope over nature and human life. These deities relation to the sun, moon, fire, etc., suggests an influence on all aspects of existence.
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - El campo lo desconoce
 - Notes: It is not known whether the supreme god's knowledge is relevant outside the region of the Otomi people. However, the influence of these deities might extend to other Mesoamerican peoples through similarities in the pantheons of surrounding cultures, like the relationship with Mexica gods (Wright Carr, 2007).
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Sí
 - Notes: Supreme Gods are associated with natural phenomena like the sun and moon, suggesting they have a visible and active presence in the outside world.
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– El campo lo desconoce
Notes: The gods' connection to phenomena like fire, rain, wind, etc., suggests they have complete knowledge of the fundamental elements affecting the world (Wright Carr, 2007).

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Sí
Notes: The supreme gods directly affect the world through creation and cosmic balance (Dow, 1974; García, 1918).

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Sí

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Sí
Notes: Old Father and Mother's influence is felt indirectly through the actions of priests, rulers, and rituals. (Dow, 1974; García, 1918).

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Sí
Notes: Both the Old Father and Old Mother show positive emotions in relation to benevolence, creation and protection (Dow, 1974; García, 1918).

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– Sí
Notes: Other supernatural beings are venerated alongside the supreme gods (Dow, 1974; García, 1918). The Otomi religion included a variety of deities within their Pantheon, including Gods like Edāhī (God of Wind), Et'axākak'èngüi (White feathered Cloud Serpent), Hmūhai (God of Earth), and Hmū'ye (God of Rain). Their close relation to the Nahuas ethnic group also meant that they shared some of their deities. Hmūhai (God of Earth) and Hmū'ye (God of Rain), for example, are also venerated by the Nahuas under the names of Tlāltēuctli and Tlaloc respectively. (Wright Carr, 2007)

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Sí

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Sí

↳ In dreams:

– Sí

↳ In trance possession:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Through divination practices:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Sí (especifique): Dreams, rituals and Intermediaries

Notes: The supreme gods communicate with the living through rituals, dreams, and intermediaries like the *bādi* (Dow, 1974; García, 1918).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Sí

Notes: The Otomi believe that the spirits of ancestors, often referred to as "tata" (fathers) or "nana" (mothers), are active in the lives of the living. These spirits are invoked during rituals to seek guidance and protection. (Carrasco Pizana, 1986)

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Sí

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Sí

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Sí

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Sí
- ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - El campo lo desconoce
 - Notes: Spirits can influence the world, especially during healing rituals where shamans interact with them (Dow, 1974; Garcia, 1918). Tata and Nana are perceived as Guide figures, but it is unclear whether they actively reward or only offer guidance.
- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Sí
 - Notes: Spirits directly influence the world through guidance and advice. (Carrasco Pizana, 1986)
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Sí
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Sí
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - El campo lo desconoce
 - Notes: Descriptions of humans spirits do not describe negative emotions.
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Sí
- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - No
- ↳ In dreams:
 - No
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
- ↳ Through divination processes:
 - No
- ↳ Only through specialists:
 - Sí
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

Notes: Gods, while associated with specific realms of influence, like rain and wind, usually take on human forms in art and other representations.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Although the bādi acts as the middleman between God and the Otomi, they are not understood as a form of divinity.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Sí

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Sí

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Sí

Notes: Some of the Otomi Gods are Bimazofo, associated with the harvest; Edāhi, the god of wind; Et'axākak'ēngüi, the white serpent of the clouds; and Hmūhai, the lord of the Earth. Hmū'ye governs the rain, while Nok'ēnmaxi, also known as Ek'ēnmaxi, represents the feathered serpent. Nopot'ejā is related to sexuality, while Noyo jwā (meaning two rabbits) is related to the Pulque and drunkenness. Zi naná, Makamé (Old Mother) and Zi dada, Makatá (Old Father) represent the Sun and the Moon respectively, although their realms of influence do not limit to a specific area. (Wright Carr, 2007)

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: In Otomi belief, shamans (bādi) act as intermediaries between humans and supernatural beings, performing rituals to communicate with these entities. However, these interactions occur only with the bādi, and only during rituals. It is unclear whether the elder spirits continue to interact with people outside of these rituals. (Carrasco Pizana, 1986)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– El campo lo desconoce

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Sí

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Sí

Notes: The bādi (Otomi shamans) use amate paper cut-outs in rituals to invoke supernatural powers. These figures represent deities or forces and serve as mediators between the bādi and the spiritual realm. They are used for healing, protection, and ensuring community well-being by channeling nzahki (vital force).

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - No
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - No
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Sí
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Sí
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Sí
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Sí
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - El campo lo desconoce

Notes: It is possible that shamans invoke the god of fertility. There are no recorded explicit mentions of this phenomena, however.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - No

- ↳ Other [specify]
 - El campo lo desconoce

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:
– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:
– Sí

Notes: The Otomi religious system includes norms and values that guide behavior, such as respect for nature, community reciprocity, and adherence to ritual practices. These norms are communicated through ceremonies, myths, and the guidance of shamans (bādi). (Sandstrom, 2009).

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:
– Sí

Notes: The Otomi distinguish between conventional norms, like those governing daily social interactions, and moral principles, which are deeply tied to their cosmology and spiritual beliefs. Moral violations, such as disrespecting sacred forces or neglecting rituals, are considered offenses against both the community and the supernatural. (Dow, 1986).

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:
– Presente y clara

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:
– Sí

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– Sí
Notes: The Otomi explicitly tie moral norms to entities such as deities and sacred forces. For instance, specific moral behaviors, such as offerings or ritual practices, are directly linked to honoring and appeasing these entities to ensure protection and favor. (Galnier, 1990, 2004)

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– Sí
Notes: Otomi morale is tied to their deities, most of which often take human forms.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– Sí

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:
– A todos los individuos de la sociedad

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):
– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

— No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

— No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

— El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Lockhart (1992) developed an extensive analysis on the Nahua practices, including fasting. It is very likely that some of these extended to the Otomi religion, but remains unclear.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

— El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

— No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

— Sí

Notes: Since ancient times, Otomi groups established a system of gifts and reciprocation with their deities. After receiving divine favors, it was necessary to offer something in return, usually blood offerings, which were the most valued by the sacred powers.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

— No

Notes: San Bernardino de Sahagun (1499-1590), wrote this about his first encounter with Otomi Shamans: "They raised and instructed the young boys there (in the temple). They performed penance for everyone: they kept vigil all night during the sacrifices, pricking or bleeding their lips or thighs with maguey spines, and at midnight, they washed themselves in the cold. They fasted and played their drum or teponaztli on top of the temple, claiming to be keeping watch and safeguarding with that musical instrument." (De Solano, 1991) While adult human sacrifices are not directly related to the Otomi cosmology, it is possible that their close relation to the Nahuas influenced their understanding of their relation with the gods.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

— No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

— No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

— El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Offerings were a common practice in Otomi Religion. These included food and valuable objects that were left for the deceased. It is unknown whether these offerings were perceived as a sacrificial act.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

— Sí

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

— No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

— Sí

Notes: Ethical principles, such as respect for nature, ancestors, and community, were integral to the religious life of the Otomi people. (Wright Carr, 2007)

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Rituals performed by shamans, and religious rituals revolving around offerings could be performed privately, but it was not a requirement. (Wright Carr, 2007)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Large-scale public ceremonies and festivals were an essential parts of religious life in the Otomi community. These rituals, such as seasonal celebrations or harvest rituals were foundational to their religious life. It is unclear whether participation was enforced upon all member of the society.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Sí

Notes: There are cultural markers such as the use of specific clothing, body paint, or symbols that identify individuals (shamans) within the group. (Wright Carr, 2005)

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– No

↳ Hair:

– No

↳ Dress:

– Sí

↳ Ornaments:

– Sí

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Sí

Notes: The gods related to creation are called Old Mother and Old Father.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Sí

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Una sociedad de jefatura

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: The Otomi religious practices include rituals aimed at ensuring successful harvests and agricultural fertility. However, there is no evidence to suggest that these religious practices provided institutionalized relief during times of famine. (Dow, 2003)

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: The Otomi religious system did not have formal institutions to address poverty. Assistance to those in need was managed through communal support and reciprocal relationships within the community, rather than through institutionalized religious mechanisms. (Martinez Ruiz, 1982)

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest that there were formal religious institutions dedicated to providing care for the elderly. The elderly did occupy an important position within the community, often called "grandfather" or "grandmother" as a sign of respect. This could suggest that some type of care could've taken place. (Martinez Ruiz, 1982)

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Education was conducted informally through oral traditions, ritual participation, and apprenticeship under shamans (bādi) or community leaders. (Galinier, 1990)

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: Otomi religious practices were organized around community leaders, shamans (bādi), and local rituals rather than formal bureaucracies. Leadership roles existed, but they were more informal and rooted in communal or familial ties rather than institutionalized bureaucratic systems. (Galinier, 1990; Lopez Austin, 1997)

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Notes: Interaction with external bureaucracies would have been limited or nonexistent before the Mexica Empire exerted influence over some Otomi territories. Even then, these interactions were more about tribute and political control than bureaucratic integration. (Smith, 2003)

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

— Sí

Notes: The Otomi communities managed their own food storage systems independently. They utilized traditional techniques, such as dehydration, to preserve surplus agricultural produce like maize and other cereals during periods of scarcity, especially in winter. These methods involved selecting dry, well-ventilated, and cool locations to store food, ensuring protection from moisture, pests, and contamination by fungi. (Bortot et al., 2012)

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

— El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Several Mesoamerican cultures had complex irrigation systems that included agricultural irrigation, the conveyance, control, and drainage of rainwater, and the regulation of water levels in lakes, swamps, and flood-prone areas. (García Sánchez, 2011) It is likely that the Otomi adopted these techniques, but there are no definite studies that confirm such behaviours existed.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

— No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Sí

Notes: The extensive network of Mesoamerican roads, including those used by the Otomi, was established and maintained by broader regional efforts. These routes facilitated trade and communication across diverse groups and regions. Long-distance trade was conducted by specialized merchants, who relied on these pathways to connect settlements and distribute goods. Along these roads, merchants could travel approximately 25 km per day while carrying over 20 kg, depending on the terrain and climate. In Nahuatl, these specialized merchants were known as tlameme (Ortiz Díaz, 2006). Although many sources confirm the existence of Otomi merchants participating in Mesoamerican trade networks, their specific name or designation is not mentioned.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

— El campo lo desconoce

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Sí

Notes: During the expansion of the Mexica Empire, the Otomi in regions like Xaltocan were required to provide tribute to the Mexica state, often in the form of agricultural products, textiles, and other goods. (Carrasco Pizana, 1986; Smith, 2003) Records also indicate that the Otomi paid tribute to other groups, such as the Chichimecas, during the 10th to 12th centuries. (Instituto Nacional de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2016)

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

— El campo lo desconoce

Notes: The Otomi did not have a religiously organized police force. Enforcement of laws and maintenance of order were the responsibilities of secular leaders, such as the local lord (señor), who also acted as a judge. The limited knowledge of pre-Hispanic Otomi culture comes from 16th-century chroniclers and geographic accounts. Compared to the Nahua, Otomi culture was considered rudimentary. The primary source is a 1582 report by royal scribe Francisco Ramos de Cárdenas, based on testimonies from elder Indigenous individuals. (Wright Carr, Lara Valdés & Contreras Soto, 2010)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Notes: Before the Spanish conquest, there is no evidence of an external police force interacting with the Otomi community. Law enforcement was managed internally by local leaders and their

subordinates (mandones). (Wright Carr, Lara Valdés & Contreras Soto, 2010)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Sí

Notes: The judicial system was intertwined with the Otomi's religious worldview. The local lord, influenced by religious customs, served as the primary judge, enforcing both communal norms and religiously informed practices. (Wright Carr, Lara Valdés & Contreras Soto, 2010)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Sí

Notes: Regions under Mexica influence were often subject to their judicial system. Many crimes or infractions were treated similarly to those within the Mexica legal framework. (Wright Carr, Lara Valdés & Contreras Soto, 2010)

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Sí

Notes: Punishments, many of which were severe and informed by religious norms, were administered under the authority of the local lord. Examples include stoning for serious theft or sexual crimes and corporal punishment for disobedience. (Wright Carr, Lara Valdés & Contreras Soto, 2010)

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Sí

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Sí

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– El campo lo desconoce

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Sí

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Sí

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Sí

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Influence of the Mexica empire over legal frameworks is present throughout the literature, but there are not enough sources to confirm that their understanding of law was entirely dependent upon them.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

— El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Few records indicate the existence of a formalized Otomi army. There are mentions, however, of an elite Mexican military order, known as the Otontin (named after the Otomi people). Conflicting sources also name these as being mercenary forces, lending their services to the Mexica Empire or the Tlaxcaltecan. (Piho, 2022)

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Sí

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Sí

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

— No

Notes: The Otomi language is not a single language but a group of four distinct dialects: Western Otomi (spoken in areas like the Mezquital Valley), Eastern Otomi (in the Sierra Madre), Tilapa Otomi (spoken in southeastern Toluca Valley), and Ixtenco Otomi (on the slopes of La Malinche volcano). These linguistic variations arose due to migrations and cultural shifts, such as the pre-Hispanic eastward and westward movements of Otomi speakers and their post-conquest migration northward. Otomi is part of the Otopamean language family, closely related to Mazahua, Matlatzinca, and Pame, all descending from a proto-Otomi language spoken centuries ago. Since ancient times, Otomi speakers have lived in diverse geographical environments and interacted with other linguistic communities. Although the Otomi possess a rich linguistic heritage with multiple dialects, there is no evidence of a unique written system tied specifically to their religious practices. Instead, they utilized the shared Mesoamerican pictographic system, which was used by various cultures in the region. (Wright Carr, 2005)

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Sí

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Sí

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

— Sí

Notes: The Otomi employed a formal calendar system rooted in the broader Mesoamerican tradition. It comprised the 260-day ritual calendar (tonalpohualli) and the 365-day solar calendar (xiuhpohualli), both central to their religious ceremonies and agricultural activities. The Otomi adapted these calendars to reflect their unique linguistic and cultural identity, as illustrated by references in documents like the Códice de Huichapan. (Pharo, 2013; Patrick-Encina, 2011)

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Notes: The Otomi calendar was shared with the broader Mesoamerican tradition. It was not, however, externally imposed by other cultures, but rather emanated from the broader plurilingual tradition in central Mesoamerica (Wright Carr, 2011)

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

— Sí

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Recolección
- Caza (incluyendo animales marinos)
- Pesca
- Agricultura a pequeña escala/jardines hortícolas o huertos
- Agricultura a gran escala (ej. monocultivos, sistemas de irrigación organizados)

Notes: The Otomí people were primarily self-sufficient in food production. Their economy was based on agriculture, cultivating crops such as maize, beans, squash, and chilies. They also engaged in hunting, fishing, and gathering wild fruits and herbs to supplement their diet. (Carrasco Pizana, 1950)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- No

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